

INTELLEKTUAL MULK

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ma'lumki intellektual mulk ijodiy aqliy faoliyat mahsulidir. Ushbu maqolada intellektual mulk majmuiga kiruvchi fan, adabiyot, san'at va ishlab chiqarish sohasida ijodiy faoliyatning boshqa turlari, adabiy, badiy, ilmiy asarlar, kashfiyotlar ixtirolar, kompyuter uchun dasturlar, firma atamalari va boshqa aqliy mulk ob'yektlari ham yoritilgan. Shuningdek ushbu maqolada hozirgi davrda intellektual mulkni muhofaza qilish muhim vazifa hisoblanadi deb fikr keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: fan, adabiyot, ilmiy asarlar, ixtirolar, kompyuter dasturlar.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Известно, что интеллектуальная собственность является продуктом творческой мыслительной деятельности. В данной статье рассматриваются иные виды творческой деятельности в области науки, литературы, искусства и производства, литературно-художественные научные произведения, открытия, изобретения, программы для ЭВМ, товарищества и другие объекты интеллектуальной собственности, входящие в состав комплекса интеллектуальной собственности. Также в данной статье высказывается мысль о том, что защита интеллектуальной собственности является важной задачей на сегодняшний день.

Ключевые слова: наука, искусства, открытия, изобретения, программы.

ABSTRACT

It is known that Intellectual Property is a product of creative mental activity. This article discusses other types of creative activity in the field of science, literature, art and production, literary and artistic scientific works, discoveries, inventions, computer programs, partnerships and other objects of Intellectual Property that are part of the Intellectual Property. This article also suggests that the protection of Intellectual Property is an important task today.

Key words: *creative, mental activity, science, computer programs, production.*

Intellectual property

Intellectual property is the name for information, ideas, works of art and other creations of the mind for which the creator has an established proprietary right of use. Intellectual property laws exist to protect creative works by ensuring that only the creators benefit from marketing them or making them available, be they individuals or corporations. Intellectual property rights for software and digital information have generated much controversy. There are those who want to ensure strict control of creators over their digital products, whereas others emphasize the importance of maintaining a strong public domain in cyberspace, and argue for unrestricted access to electronic information and for the permissibility of copying proprietary software. In computer ethics, the ethical and philosophical aspects of these disputes are analyzed, and policy proposals are made for the regulation of digital intellectual property in its different forms.

Intellectual property (IP) refers to “creations of the mind,” such as literary and artistic works, inventions, and “symbols, names, images, and designs used in commerce.”¹ It is generally divided into three categories: copyright, trademark, and patents. In China, each of these is protected by civil law, criminal law, administrative law, and other laws. Furthermore, such protection has been applied to proprietary interests in cyberspace. This chapter mainly examines three types of IP infringement, namely, copyright infringement, trademark infringement, and patent infringement. It is

particularly concerned with how these infringements have emerged in cyberspace and how they have been addressed by Chinese law and regulations.

Types of Intellectual Property¹

Do you know what is the difference is between a patent and an industrial design, how to protect your photo with a copyright, or why you would want to obtain a protected designation of origin? Discover everything you ever wanted to know about IP rights.

Patents

A patent is an exclusive right granted for an invention. Generally speaking, a patent provides the patent owner with the right to decide how-or whether-the invention can be used by others.

Copyright

Copyright is a legal term used to describe the rights that creators have over their literary and artistic works. Works covered by copyright range from books, music, paintings, sculpture and films, to computer programs, databases, advertisements, maps and technical drawings.

Trademarks

A trademark is a sign capable of distinguishing the goods or services of one enterprise from those of other enterprises. Trademarks date back to ancient times when artisans used to put their signature or “mark” on their products.

Industrial designs

An industrial design constitute the ornamental or aesthetic aspect of an article. A design may consist of three-dimensional features, such as the shape or surface of an article, or two-dimensional features, such as patters, lines or color.

Geographical indications ²

Geographical indications and appellations of origin are signs used on goods that have a specific geographical origin and possess qualities, a reputation or characteristic

¹ Intellectual Property Securitization, 2021.

² . Incorporation Intellectual Property Protection Provisions in FTA, 2019.

that are essentially attributable to that place of origin. Most commonly, a geographical indication includes the name of the place of origin of the goods.

Trade secrets

Trade secrets are IP rights on confidential information which may be sold or licensed. The unauthorized acquisition, use or disclosure of such secret information in a manner contrary to honest commercial practices by others is regarded as an unfair practice and a violation of the trade secret protection.

CONCLUSION

Intellectual Property rights reward creativity and human endeavor, which fuel is the progress of humankind. Understanding the country's IP rights and following the best practices can drastically reduce the risk of losing the company's Intellectual Property.

Indian government has initiated various steps towards Intellectual Property Rights Protection. Do not use competitor's mark in such way that it harms competitor in unfair way.

Documentation of indigenous and local knowledge systems in electronic format, therefore, of prime importance, especially for the developing countries, which have a rich abundance of this knowledge.

Create yourself, rather than using other's creators.

The competition is a healthy, but competitors should create own original technology, not stolen or steal someone's.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

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